

Reheat flames response to entropy waves

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Abstract

Sequential combustion architectures rely on auto-ignition flame stabilization in the second stage combustor. Due to the exponential temperature dependence of the ignition delay time the second stage flames can respond to hot spots generated by unsteady first stage combustion. In this paper, the auto-ignition flame response is investigated by extending an existing analytical model for acoustic waves so that it also accounts for entropy waves. Explicit expressions for the flame transfer functions and linear to non-linear transition thresholds are derived. Results for different operating conditions, forcing amplitudes and frequencies are discussed. For this, three computational domains of increasing complexity are considered for model validation: a 2D duct, a 3D backward facing step, and finally a full-scale Ansaldo Energia GT26 sequential combustor. Unsteady Reynold-averaged Navier-Stokes as well as large-eddy simulations are performed. Acoustic and entropic contributions of the flame response are separated by means of system identification techniques. Finally, non-linear flame transfer functions are identified. It is observed that the gains linearly increase with the excitation frequency and non-linear, frequency dependent effects are observed already for small amplitude levels of excitation.

Keywords: Entropy waves, auto-ignition flames, flame transfer function, non-linearities, gas turbines

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1. Introduction

In an early work, Zeldovich [1] introduces the concept of ‘spontaneous propagation’, separating it from flame deflagration and detonation and remarking that “for this regime a strong dependence of the propagation rate on initial conditions (in particular, on initial temperature) is characteristic, as well as its independence of heat conductivity of the gas and of the speed of sound”. Today, these flames are commonly referred to as auto-ignition or reheat flames and a good understanding of their physics is available in the literature [2–8]. Compared to deflagration flames they do not depend on diffusive processes to propagate, but on the spontaneous radical build up in the high temperature unburnt mixture [2]. Gas turbines with sequential combustion architecture, as used in Ansaldo Energia GT26 and GT36, are designed to exploit auto-ignition flame properties ensuring stability in a high velocity flow. In these systems, entropy waves can be generated by unsteady combustion in the first stage or cooling air modulation, which are subsequently convected to the sequential combustor, where they can cause heat release modulation [6, 9]. The phenomenon is depending on the operating condition, excitation amplitude and frequency and non-linearities can arise even at low forcing amplitudes. Its understanding is of significant importance in the engine design. In the present paper, the dynamic response of reheat flames to fluctuations in the hot gas inlet temperature is investigated numerically and analytically.

Numerical results for reheat flames are obtained in a series of works by Bothien and co-workers [6, 10, 11]. Flame transfer functions (FTF) and matrices at engine conditions are identified by means of suitable identification techniques both in the linear and non-linear range. Also Schulz and Noiray [7, 9] characterize the dynamic response of reheat flames. In particular, the effect of entropy waves is systematically analyzed performing system identification and LES to obtain linear and non-linear flame transfer functions [7]. The driving mechanism of the unsteady heat release modulations is identified in the appearance of auto-ignition kernels in the burner as a result of inlet temperature modulations. Analytic studies on the response of reheat flames to acoustic disturbances are conducted by Ni et al. [12] and later extended by Zellhuber et al. [8, 13]. The latter introduce a plug flow reactor model and evaluate the effect of isentropic pressure modulations on the chemical reaction rates, identifying two mechanisms responsible for unsteady heat release rates: a non-zero average effect on the mean ignition delay time of the mixture, prevalent at low frequencies and an instantaneous effect of the pres-

Figure 1: Sketch of the model setup. x_f : flame position, x_i : domain inlet, \bar{u} : mean flow velocity, τ : ignition delay time, f, g : Riemann invariants (down- and upstream travelling acoustic waves).

sure fluctuations at the flame location on the heat release rate, which is important at high frequencies. Recently, Gant et al. [11], set-up an analytic model able to capture non-linear effects of auto-ignition flames subject to temperature excitation.

Several publications [6, 7, 9–11] report large gains as well as early onset of non-linearities for autoignition flames forced by entropic fluctuations. Additionally, they unanimously conclude that temperature forcing has a major effect on the flame compared to acoustic forcing. The aim of the present paper is to propose and validate an explanation of the phenomenon extending the acoustic model of Zellhuber et al. [8]. In particular, this will provide an analytical expression for the observed non-linear phenomena, which currently is not available.

2. Analytical Model formulation

An idealized configuration is considered to model the effects of entropy waves on the flame dynamics. It consists of a straight duct in which the injected perfectly premixed fuel/air mixture is treated as a series of plug flow reactors, see Fig. 1. The equivalence ratio of the mixture is assumed to be constant, an analysis of its effect can be found in [10, 13]. In this setup, high convective flow velocities at elevated temperatures typical of sequential combustors cause auto-ignition to be the only flame stabilization mechanism. A reactor injected into the domain at time t_i is convected downstream by the mean flow \bar{u} and ignites approximately after a time $\bar{\tau}$, the auto-ignition delay time of the mixture. The reactor radical build-up is governed by a normalized progress variable c , which spans the interval $[0, 1]$ from unburnt to burnt conditions; the progress variable temporal evolution will be affected by the reactor mean temperature and by acoustic fluctuations. For the present study the

heat release rate can be expressed as (see [8]):

$$\dot{Q}(t) = \int_{-\infty}^t \Delta h_F \dot{m}_f(t_i) \dot{\omega}_c(t, t_i) dt_i \quad (1)$$

where Δh_F is the fuel lower heating value, $\dot{m}_f(t_i)$ is the fuel mass flow injected at time t_i and $\dot{\omega}_c(t, t_i)$ is the source term associated to the progress variable c . Equation (1) is integrated, for a fixed time t , over all the reactors injected into the domain, each one contributing to the overall heat release with its own reaction source term $\dot{\omega}_c(t, t_i)$ at the time t .

The fuel mass flow rate can be rewritten as $\dot{m}_f(t_i) = \bar{m}_f + \dot{m}'_f(t_i)$, where \bar{m}_f is the constant mean value and $\dot{m}'_f(t_i)$ is the perturbation. This last term is different for each reactor and depends on the inlet conditions at which the reactor is injected. We express $\dot{\omega}_c(t, t_i)$ as:

$$\dot{\omega}_c(t, t_i) = \bar{\omega}_c(t - t_i) + \tilde{\omega}_c(t - t_i, t_i) + \dot{\omega}'_c(t, t_i) \quad (2)$$

The first term of Eq. (2) is the source term of an unperturbed homogeneous 0D reactor at mean inlet pressure and temperature. In the absence of acoustic and entropic disturbances, this would be the only term present. The heat release rate given by this term at each time t does not depend on the time t itself but just on the residence time of the reactor in the domain $t - t_i := \Delta t_i$.

The second term $\tilde{\omega}_c(\Delta t_i, t_i)$ takes into account entropic disturbances. An entropic perturbation of the inlet temperature at time t_i results in an injected plug flow reactor with a modified heat release source term, where the heat release is advanced/retarded with respect to the mean conditions for a hotter/colder mixture. This perturbation of the source term is a property of each reactor and it is convected downstream with the reactor itself. The heat release rate depends just on the reactor t_i and its residence time Δt_i .

The third term $\dot{\omega}'_c(t, t_i)$ is a perturbation due to acoustic disturbances. The isentropic pressure and velocity fluctuations tend to have a zero mean value (larger and smaller pressures will alternate), nevertheless they accumulate their effects over the plug residence time and can affect the heat release rate. Additionally they can instantaneously change the pressure at the flame location and result in significant heat release rate fluctuations, especially for high frequencies ($f > 1000$ Hz). In contrast to the first two terms, they directly depend on the time t . For a more detailed discussion on this term, the reader is referred to Zellhuber *et al.* [8].

In Eq. (2) we assume that, for small amplitude perturbations, acoustic and entropic effects on the heat release rate $\dot{\omega}_c(t, t_i)$ are decoupled, which in an earlier work is shown to be valid [6].

Inserting the two contributions into Eq. (1), neglecting all second order terms, subtracting and dividing by the mean heat release $\bar{Q} = \Delta h_F \bar{m}_f$ we obtain:

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{\dot{Q}'(t)}{\bar{Q}} &= \int_{-\infty}^t \left[\frac{\dot{m}'_f(t_i)}{\bar{m}_f} \bar{\omega}_c(\Delta t_i) + \tilde{\omega}_c(\Delta t_i, t_i) + \dot{\omega}'_c(t, t_i) \right] dt_i \\ &= \int_{-\infty}^t \left[\left(\frac{u'(x_i, t_i)}{\bar{u}} + \frac{1}{\gamma} \frac{p'(x_i, t_i)}{\bar{p}} - \frac{\gamma - 1}{\gamma} \frac{s'(x_i, t_i)}{R} \right) \right. \\ &\quad \left. \dots \bar{\omega}_c(\Delta t_i) + \tilde{\omega}_c(\Delta t_i, t_i) + \dot{\omega}'_c(t, t_i) \right] dt_i \end{aligned} \quad (3)$$

where in the last calculation step the mass fuel fluctuations at the inlet x_i are expressed in terms of pressure $p'(x_i, t_i)$, velocity $u'(x_i, t_i)$ and entropy $s'(x_i, t_i)$ fluctuations. The first, the second and the last contributions to the heat release fluctuations in Eq. (3) are of acoustic nature (see [8]), the other two are entropic. We focus on the entropic ones and describe them more in-depth in Sec. 2.1.

2.1. Entropic part

The entropic part of Eq. (3) reads:

$$\frac{\dot{Q}'_e(t)}{\bar{Q}} = \int_{-\infty}^t \left[\frac{1 - \gamma}{\gamma} \frac{s'(x_i, t_i)}{R} \bar{\omega}_c(t - t_i) + \tilde{\omega}_c(\Delta t_i, t_i) \right] dt_i \quad (4)$$

To understand the physical meaning of the two terms in Eq. (4) we report the linearized non-isentropic relations for an ideal gas:

$$\frac{T'}{\bar{T}} = \frac{\gamma - 1}{\gamma} \frac{s'}{R} + \frac{\gamma - 1}{\gamma} \frac{p'}{\bar{p}} \quad (5a)$$

$$\frac{\rho'}{\bar{\rho}} = -\frac{\gamma - 1}{\gamma} \frac{s'}{R} + \frac{1}{\gamma} \frac{p'}{\bar{p}} \quad (5b)$$

In absence of acoustic fluctuations, i.e. $p'(x_i, t_i) = 0$, entropic fluctuations at the inlet result in temperature and density fluctuations according to Eqs. (5). As can be seen, the two are equal in magnitude and opposite in sign: an increase in inlet temperature is accompanied by a decrease in density and vice-versa. They both contribute to the unsteady heat release rate.

Given the assumption of constant equivalence ratio, a density fluctuation does not affect the chemistry of a plug but results in larger amounts of fuel and therefore increased heat release rates. The steady state source term $\bar{\omega}_c(\Delta t_i)$ in Eq. (4) is indeed directly modulated by the density of the plug $\rho'/\bar{\rho} = -(\gamma - 1)s'/(\gamma R)$.

The effect of temperature fluctuations in turn is directly affecting the heat release term $\tilde{\omega}_c(\Delta t_i, t_i)$; physically a larger/smaller temperature modifies the chemical kinetics reducing/increasing the auto-ignition delay

Figure 2: Left: ignition delay time of a homogeneous mixture of air and methane for different temperatures. Right: temperature and heat release rate profile over time. Results obtained from 0-dimensional Cantera simulations.

time. In contrast to the case of a modulation of density, each plug is still releasing the same amount of energy over its life time, however, its profile over the residence time Δt_i is different.

To derive an expression for the flame transfer function for entropy waves we introduce a model for the reaction source terms:

$$\begin{aligned} \dot{\omega}_c(\Delta t_i, t_i) &= \bar{\omega}_c(\Delta t_i) + \tilde{\omega}_c(\Delta t_i, t_i) = \\ &= \frac{1}{\sqrt{2\pi\sigma^2}} \exp\left[-\frac{1}{2}\left(\frac{\Delta t_i - \tau_0 e^{B(T(x_i, t_i) - \bar{T})}}{\sigma}\right)^2\right] \end{aligned} \quad (6)$$

where $\bar{\omega}_c(\Delta t_i)$ is the mean contribution ($T(x_i, t_i) = \bar{T}$) and $\tilde{\omega}_c(\Delta t_i, t_i) = \dot{\omega}_c(\Delta t_i, t_i) - \bar{\omega}_c(\Delta t_i)$ is the remaining fluctuation. As is commonly done for modeling delayed terms in thermoacoustics, the heat release rate of a single reactor over its residence time Δt_i is assumed to have a Gaussian distribution with width σ around a mean ignition delay time $\tau = \tau_0 \exp[B(T(x_i, t_i) - \bar{T})]$. For a reactor with mean inlet temperature \bar{T} , the mean ignition delay time will be τ_0 , whereas for perturbed reactors the deviation from τ_0 will depend on the small negative constant B . Fluctuations in the inlet temperature modify the distribution width σ , the effect is neglected as second order. Different fuels and blends result in large variations of ignition delay time τ_0 and flame thickness σ , showing different sensitivity to fluctuations in the temperature (B). For example, changes of τ_0 of an order of magnitude are typical when switching from methane to hydrogen flames. The formulation as in Eq. (6) allows to lump this complexity in three parameters, which need to be properly re-evaluated as the fuel blend or the operating conditions change. A physical interpretation of B , τ_0 and σ is displayed in Fig. 2.

Considering a sinusoidal inlet temperature fluctuation $T'(x_i, t_i)/\bar{T} = (\gamma - 1)s'(x_i, t_i)/(\gamma R) = \Delta T/\bar{T} \sin(\omega t_i)$, the integral in Eq. (4) together with the ansatz in Eq. (6), truncated to the first order in ΔT and transformed to the

frequency domain results in:

$$\frac{\dot{Q}'}{\bar{Q}} = -\tau_0 B \omega \bar{T} i e^{-i\omega\tau_0} e^{-\omega^2\sigma^2/2} \frac{T'}{\bar{T}} + e^{-i\omega\tau_0} e^{-\omega^2\sigma^2/2} \frac{\rho'}{\bar{\rho}} \quad (7)$$

Both density and temperature fluctuations are convected to the flame by the mean flow ($e^{-i\omega\tau_0}$) and, for small delays $\omega\tau_0 \ll 1$, result in heat release rate fluctuations in phase with the density and in quadrature with respect to the temperature. At low frequencies the gain of the density is constant ($e^{-\omega^2\sigma^2/2} \approx 1$) whereas the temperature shows a linearly increasing gain with the frequency. This term can reach large values before being low-pass filtered. This intrinsic feature of the flame is captured by the term $e^{-\omega^2\sigma^2/2}$, see Sec. 4.1.

Equation (7) is valid in the linear regime. To be able to predict the transition from linear to non-linear flame response for increasing temperature forcing we evaluate the integral in Eq. (4) up to the second order in T'/\bar{T} and extract the amplitude of the second harmonic. We assume the system to respond linearly as long as the ratio between the second and the first harmonic is smaller than 1/10, i.e. the second harmonic is one order of magnitude smaller than the fundamental one. This results in a linearity criterion:

$$-\frac{1}{2} B \sqrt{4\omega^2\tau_0^2 + 1} \Delta T e^{-3\omega^2\sigma^2/2} < \frac{1}{10} \quad (8)$$

Large ignition delay times τ_0 and excitation amplitudes ΔT_0 render the system more prone to exhibit nonlinearities. A non-monotonic behavior is observed with respect to the excitation frequency ω , with small and large frequencies presenting broader linear ranges.

2.2. Diffusion, dispersion and turbulence

The model derivation carried out in Sec. 2.1 is based on the assumption that the different plug flow reactors do not interact with each other. In reality, turbu-

Figure 3: Snapshots of the temperature field of the backward facing step (left) and the Ansaldo Energia GT26 sequential burner (right).

lence, dispersion and inhomogeneities will mix the different plugs, reducing the effective forcing amplitude ΔT . Even for simplified geometries diffusion effects will tend to smoothen out any temperature gradients in the flow and the effective temperature wave amplitude seen by the flame will be smaller. All these phenomena are taken into account by introducing a transfer function

$$F(\omega) = \exp\left[\frac{\text{Pe}}{2}\left(1 - \sqrt{1 + 4i\omega\tau_c\text{Pe}^{-1}}\right)\right] \quad (9)$$

which relates forcing amplitudes at the inlet to forcing amplitudes at a downstream location, usually the burner exit. τ_c is the convective delay between injection and the reference downstream location, Pe is the Peclet number, a measure of the relative importance between convective and diffusive processes. Equation (9) can be obtained as solution of a one dimensional convection-diffusion problem. We use it here as black box to take into account also dispersion and turbulence. The Peclet number can be interpreted as capability of the burner to filter out disturbances, with smaller numbers meaning more filtering.

3. Numerical simulations

The validation of the model introduced in Sec. 2, is done with the commercial software ANSYS Fluent v18.2. Three sets of simulations on computational domains with increasing complexity are performed: a 2D straight duct (2D), a 3D backward facing step (BFS) and the Ansaldo Energia GT26 sequential burner (SEV). Figure 3 presents the latter two.

For the two-dimensional straight duct, incompressible URANS are performed with a structured mesh consisting of $2.5 \cdot 10^5$ quadrilateral cells. At the velocity inlet the hot gas composition is kept constant. Fuel and air are perfectly premixed and a sinusoidal temperature forcing is applied. At the outlet the pressure is imposed. The bottom and top walls are stationary non-slip adiabatic walls. All transported quantities are discretized by a second order spatial and first order implicit temporal scheme and solved by a pressure-based transient solver (SIMPLE).

For the three-dimensional backward-facing step (BFS), compressible LES are performed. The mesh consists of $2.11 \cdot 10^6$ hexahedral cells, refined at the step and flame locations to better resolve the chemistry and the fluid dynamics. The bottom wall is an adiabatic, no-slip wall, whereas the top one is stationary with zero shear stress and zero heat flux. Periodic boundary conditions are applied on the side surfaces. At the velocity inlet, fully premixed conditions are imposed. The outlet is set to acoustically non-reflecting so as to avoid reflections of acoustic waves, which potentially could cause thermoacoustic instabilities. A second order spatial and temporal discretization scheme is used for all transported quantities, except for the momentum equation which uses the bounded central difference scheme. Turbulence scales larger than the mesh size are computed, whereas the Smagorinsky–Lilly subgrid-scale model with dynamic stress, dynamic energy flux, and a Prandtl number of 0.85 has been used to characterize the smaller scales. The turbulent Schmidt number is set to 0.7 for scalar flux and for species.

For the full-scale GT26 SEV reheat combustor, also compressible LES are performed. The same numerical setup as used for the BFS applies.

In all three geometries, the combustion is modeled with an in-house tool [14] relying on tabulated chemistry. Homogeneous reactor simulations are performed and quantities of interest are recorded. In addition, a progress variable is computed, to represent the chemistry development history. The transport equation of the mixture fraction and of the composite progress variable are solved and the quantities of interest are read from the homogeneous reactor tables. The inlet conditions are slightly different in all three setups and correspond to high pressure ($\bar{p} > 20$ bar), reheat relevant ($\bar{T} > 1000$ K, $\bar{u} \approx 100$ m/s) gas turbine operating conditions. The fuel is methane ($\phi \approx 0.5$).

4. Results

4.1. Two-dimensional duct

In total, 220 unsteady simulations with sinusoidal excitation of the inlet temperature are performed, encom-

Figure 4: FTF to temperature forcing at different amplitudes from 2D simulations. Symbols: harmonic simulations; lines: broadband forcing. The solid black line is the analytical result of Eq. (7). $f = U/L$ Sr, with $U/L \approx 167$ 1/s.

passing 55 different frequencies and 4 different excitation amplitudes ($T'/\bar{T} = [0.15, 0.38, 0.76, 1.15]\%$). Additionally, 4 broadband simulations are conducted, for which the inlet temperature is excited with a discrete random binary signal (DRBS) at the same amplitudes. The unsteady fluctuations of temperature and density at the inlet and of the overall integrated heat release rate in the domain are extracted and compared with the analytical results presented in Sec. 2.1. For this purpose, a single-input single-output (SISO) identification technique summarized in Yang et al. [10] is applied. Due to incompressibility, acoustic effects on the flame response modeling can be neglected [15]. All results are plotted with respect to the Strouhal number $Sr = fL/U$, for which the frequency is scaled with the duct length $L = 0.6$ m and mean flow velocity $U = 100$ m/s.

Figure 4 depicts the identified FTFs resulting from the different simulation approaches. Symbols represent harmonic simulation results featuring the largest signal-to-noise ratio and consequently are the most accurate. A drop in the gain is observed with increasing excitation amplitude. This is due to a non-linear response of the flame which not only responds at the excitation frequency f but also at higher harmonics resulting in a reduction of gain at the forcing frequency. For the two lowest excitation amplitudes of 0.15% and 0.38%, the flame response is linear resulting in the same identified gain and a good match with the analytical result of

Eq. (7) depicted by the solid black line.

Additionally to the harmonic forcing, the flame is also excited with broadband signals of varying amplitude. The resulting gain and phase are plotted as dashed/dotted lines in Fig. 4. For the two lower amplitudes, which are in the linear range, no significant difference is observed with respect to the results of the harmonic case, hence, validating the SISO identification technique. In the non-linear range, as expected, a drop in the identified gain can be observed. Also, a significant difference in gain between harmonic and broadband FTF is present: the non-linear response of the system at a given frequency f is influenced by higher order harmonics, which are wrongly identified by the SISO technique as a linear system response to the forcing at frequency f . Consequently, the correct non-linear flame functions relating temperature waves to heat release oscillations are given by the harmonic results (symbols) in Fig. 4, and not the ones from the broadband forcing case (lines).

In conclusion, the linearly increasing FTF gain results in a relatively large system response already at low frequencies. This is coherent with Eq. (7) and with results of different numerical studies in the literature [6, 10] and is of importance for designing stable reheat combustors. Due to diffusion and dispersion processes kicking in at elevated frequencies the inlet temperature fluctuation is considerably reduced when reaching the flame front and hence the gain decreases accordingly.

To capture the transition from linear to non-linear system response, Fig. 5 depicts in red the contour of the amplitude ratio of 2nd to 1st harmonic equal to 1/10 as defined in Eq. (8). The flame response is linear for small excitation amplitudes $\Delta T/\bar{T}$ and becomes non-linear as the amplitude increases. A new aspect presented here is that the system transition from linear to non-linear response is also frequency dependent. In particular at low and high frequencies, the system tends to behave linearly up to higher amplitudes, whereas in the mid frequency range non-linear effects appear earlier. In Fig. 4, the mismatch between identified gains with different harmonic amplitude forcing is large in the mid frequency range, whereas the low and, to a minor extent, the high frequency bands are correctly identified also by large fluctuation amplitudes. The red threshold in Fig. 5 is well reproduced by the analytic model Eq. (8) (solid white). The sensitivity to auto-ignition delay times variations is plotted with dashed lines, where smaller τ_0 correspond to larger linear domains.

Figure 5: Amplitude ratio of 2nd to 1st harmonic over forcing amplitude and frequency. Harmonic simulations. Solid red: Transition of linear to non-linear regime defined in Sec. 2.1 (ratio equal to 1/10); solid white: Eq. (8); dashed white: 30% variation of the mean ignition delay time τ_0 . $f = U/L$ Sr, with $U/L \approx 167$ 1/s.

4.2. Backward-facing step and GT26 SEV

For both the BFS and SEV geometry, a set of 3 independent compressible simulations is performed. A suitable system identification technique is used to identify the flame transfer function to entropy waves. In the compressible LES, the inlet temperature forcing is in fact exciting the pressure and velocity fields, therefore, the unsteady integrated heat release rate is given by the superposition of entropic and acoustics effects which need to be properly separated. We apply a standard identification methodology [16] based on a linear time invariant system assumption for the flame. The procedure is explained in detail by Bothien et al. [6]. In the following, only the temperature FTF is presented. The other terms can be found in [6, 10].

Figure 6 shows the identified FTF of the BFS based on different simulations. The FTF identified for the incompressible case with 0.38% excitation amplitude is the most accurate of the results, featuring a low forcing amplitude and avoiding acoustics effects. Indeed the match with the analytical result of Eq. (7) and the 4 harmonic compressible simulations is remarkable. The two compressible broadband simulations show a different behavior. The low amplitude case (0.38%) is following the linearly increasing trend with good accuracy, showing the system identification routine capability of correctly separating acoustics from entropic contributions. The high amplitude case (0.76%) is underestimating the flame gain, especially at large frequencies. This is coherent with the 2D results of Fig. 4 and is due to non-linear effects in the flame response. Note that an early onset of non-linear effects was already docu-

Figure 6: Backward-facing step FTF. Solid red and blue: Compressible LES/SI MISO identification; dash-dotted violet: Incompressible LES/SI SISO; green diamonds: compressible LES/SI MISO identification (harmonic forcing); dashed black: analytical model Eq. (7).

mented in literature for a very similar setup [13]. The phase is correctly captured by all simulations.

Figure 7 presents the normalized results obtained for the SEV. The burner-flame transfer function (BFTF, solid black) is the product between the burner transfer function (BTF, continuous red, here modeled by Eq. (9)) and the flame transfer function (FTF, solid blue, Eq. (7)), where the mean temperature \bar{T} and the mean convective flow time of a methane molecule from injection to the flame τ_0 have been extracted from the LES. The three results have been independently obtained applying multi-input multi-output and multi-input single-output (MISO) identification techniques to compressible LES. Compared to the 2D duct and the BFS, in this case turbulence and inhomogeneities play a significant role which is reflected in a steeply decreasing burner transfer function. The inlet forcing amplitude was set to values well above the non-linear threshold of Fig. 5 to overcome all signal losses in the burner. The analytical match correctly predicts the global trend. Given the simplicity, the match to this full-scale real-world combustor is remarkable.

5. Conclusions

In the present study, an existing model [8] for re-heat FTF to acoustic perturbations is extended to include entropic disturbances and verified with respect to compressible and incompressible URANS and LES, on three different domains of increasing geometrical complexity. A linear FTF is derived as function of physical

Figure 7: Transfer functions of the GT26 SEV combustor. Results extracted from MISO identification of LES (solid lines). The dashed lines are the analytical formulations of Eq. (9) (BTF, red), Eq. (7) (FTF, black) and their product (BFTF, blue).

parameters and their relative importance is discussed. Additionally, a linear to non-linear threshold condition is introduced featuring a frequency dependent variation of the limit, with intermediate frequencies more prone to exhibit non-linear effects. Both results have been confirmed by the 2D duct and BFS simulations, from which FTFs and FDFs have been extracted. Additionally, this allowed to re-validate SISO and MISO identification methodologies reported in the literature. In particular, the observation of how they become less and less accurate as the excitation amplitudes approach the non-linear range compared to harmonic simulations. The analytic model shows good agreement to simulations for a real-world, full-scale GT26 SEV combustor confirming the findings for the simplified geometries.

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